

Technology Literacy As 21st Century Teaching Skills in the Classroom: A Phenomenological Study

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Abstract. This study unveiled the teachers' experiences on 21st-century teaching skills in the classroom by analyzing their experiences and how the teachers cope with the challenges in accentuating 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom, particularly in technological literacy. The researcher collected data from ten (10) public elementary teachers assigned at the five (5) respective schools in Bunawan District, Division of Davao City. Furthermore, the researcher chose two (2) informants from the schools who are said to be beginning teachers with at least three to five years of teaching service and have experience being observed in the classroom. Using the qualitative type of research, the result revealed two themes for Figure Three, which were described as the live experiences of the teachers. Teachers mentioned and revealed during the interview, namely, improved instructional and active learning processes. Meanwhile, the teachers grasped the fourth figure with two themes, describing how they cope with technological literacy. First was the teaching process's efficiency, the students' differentiated instruction, and the slow internet connection. Lastly, figure five, in the educational insight of the teachers, exemplifies three themes drawn and observed during the interview. These were enough technological tools, enhanced teaching performance, and joining training and seminars.

KEY WORDS

1. technological literacy 2. 21st Century Skill 3. teaching competence

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1. Introduction

The integration of technology is a trend in education nowadays. For the past years, schools around the world have implemented technology that aims to ensure the success of the teaching and learning process. By fostering such a new approach in education, our system has become transformative in synthesizing information, weighing perspectives critically, and incorporating inquiries with the creation of online teaching. In the same concepts, pedagogy enables teachers to understand the best suitable practices for a classroom setting. It helps them to know how different students learn and grasp information so that they can tailor their lessons to satisfy those needs. It is likely to improve the quality of teaching and the way it is received by the students. Effective digital education is designed to provide sufficient contact, instruction, evaluation, and interaction that makes the online course as effective as the teaching and learning experience. Truly, this technological shift from knowledge being fixed at a particular time and

place has become knowledge that being accessible at any time and at any place creates the potential change in the way of learning (Gold, 2001). Additionally, Baylen, (2009), stated that teaching through technology provides teachers with an opportunity to get more involved with technology as well as their technological skills; use technology more innovatively to enhance teaching and learning; meet the needs of students at a distance, increase flexibility in working hours and locations; respond to students' requests for online educational opportunities; interact with students more frequently; respond to administration's initiative and to enhance teaching skills and productivity. In the global setting particularly in North American countries, the virtual schools are expected to grow at 13% In the National setting, Philippine E-teaching is a method of teaching that uses technology to enhance the learning of the graduate students as well as the teacher's productivity. It offers modular courses wherein most of the lessons will be conducted online to cater to the needs of students who cannot attend regular classes due to demand of work in most places in the country (Alday, and Pascual, 2012). While, there is a dearth of material in the Philippines about secondary school teachers' use of technology for instruction and learning during the global COVID-19 pandemic. Fabito, Trillanes, and Sarmiento's (2020) pertinent findings provide a foundation for students to have successful online learning experiences, while also confirming that faculty members and students were not prepared for this pandemic-related period of time for learning remotely. For instance, Balmeo et al. (2014), Garzon, Kim, and Kim (2019),

and Javier and Dirain (2019) emphasized the connection between students' academic performance and the use of technology in teaching and learning. In the local setting, In Bunawan District, Division of Davao City, it is becoming more and more clear that teachers need to be technologically literate. Since digital tools and resources are developing at a rapid pace, it is crucial to include technology into classroom instruction in order to help students develop 21st-century abilities. However, without the right assistance and training, a lot of teachers find it difficult to navigate this digital environment. Thus, it is essential to fund professional development initiatives that give teachers the chance to improve their technical literacy in order to give them the tools necessary to successfully use technology to promote student achievement. Indeed, technology literacy indicates basic areas of knowledge particularly the technological knowledge such as productivity, research, communication and media that would result to teaching proficiency particularly the in a form of educational experiences, the teaching proficiency that is depicted as cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence (Lawrence, and Veena, 2018; Ganza, 2012). The researcher finds it urgent to conduct the study on how does the 21st century teaching skills particularly technological literacy affects the teaching and learning inside the classroom This to serves as their advantage in teaching and giving quite access to global information in quality teaching through the use of internet and other information media. They can influence and make changes to the lives of their students.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The main objective of conducting this study was the 21st-century teaching skills in the classroom by means of analyzing their experiences, and how teachers cope with the challenges in accentuating 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom, particularly in technological literacy. Teachers play vital roles in the lives of the students in their classrooms. Teachers are best known for the role of educating the students that are placed in their care. Beyond that, teachers serve many other roles in the classroom. Teachers set the tone of their classrooms,

build a warm environment, mentor and nurture students, become role models, and listen and look for signs of trouble.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intended to gain insight into the experiences of teachers in accentuating 21st-century teaching skills in the classroom. In which that these experiences are very useful to generate improvement on their teaching strategies and to proceed on an empowered instructional process. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the teachers' experiences on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom?
- (2) How do teachers cope with challenges in using technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom?
- (3) What are the insights that can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—This study would serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies. To ensure an understanding of the terms used in the study, the following are defined conceptually and operationally: Technological Literacy is defined as using, following, and profiting from it in social situations as well as being able to solve problems with it (Çoklar and Şahin, 2014). In this study, it was used to define as being knowl-

edgeable in using technological tools inside the classroom. 21st-century Skills refer to abilities that progressively call for inventiveness, tenacity, and problem-solving coupled with effective teamwork (Duncan, 2009). In this study, these skills refer to skills in the following domains: digital citizenship, critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making; creativity and innovation; communication and collaboration; research and information fluency; and technology operations and concepts.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The output of this study would benefit the following: School heads and Administrators. The data and information collected on this study would serve as a platform for the school heads and administrators in creating dynamic schemes in his or her supervision of school activities for the betterment of the school as well as of the teachers by means of helping them grow particularly on their empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and

teaching proficiency teachers. They can also become the motivational driving force to keep the burning passion of the teachers in serving the young minds of this generation. Teachers. This study would also be significant because the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influences teachers' Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency, as well as their improvement of teaching competencies and their effective progress with the teaching and learning process as they serve as the wheel of education and the facilitator of learning.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This qualitative research was based on the Community of Inquiry Model proposed by Garrison et al. (2000), as cited by Ganza (2012). The Community of Inquiry Model emphasizes the relationship between higher education and technological lit-

eracy through educational experiences that depict three distinct presences in technological literacy: social, cognitive, and teaching presences. This study was also guided by Johann Friedrich. Johann Friedrich Herbart's educational philosophy and pedagogy (4 May 1776

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

– 14 August 1841) highlighted the correlation between personal development and the resulting benefits to society. According to Herbart, abilities were not innate but could be instilled, so a thorough education could provide the framework for moral and intellectual development. In order to develop an educational paradigm that would provide an intellectual base that would lead to a consciousness of social responsibility. Moreover, this study also used technological knowledge as the key knowledge area of technological literacy that was mainly derived from the TPACK framework by Ouyang and Scharber (2018). Technological knowledge is depicted as the knowledge of technology area where the instructor or the distance teachers enacted a high level of TPACK proficiency, particularly the technological knowledge within his or her teach-

ing proficiency. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework and serves as the schemata of the study. This research held into the idea of scrutinizing and influential experiences of the teachers in engaging the technology literacy as 21st century skills inside the classroom. This also aims to engage and empower their instructional process by means of classroom observations. Moreover, this also serves as an immediate response to those modifications that every teacher must acquire in order to flourish their effectiveness, particularly in the instructional process, as well as to promote life-long learning and continuous professional development. In this study, the Venn Diagram shown exemplifies the connectivity between the experiences of teachers, how teachers cope with challenges, and the possible insights gained from the study.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the research design, research participant, philosophical assumptions, research instrument, trustworthiness of the study, data collection, role of the researcher, data

analysis, trustworthiness of the study data collection, and ethical consideration. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Philosophy was defined as the use of abstract ideas and beliefs to inform research. Philosophical assumptions were typically the first ideas in developing a study, but as Lynham and Lincoln (2011) stated, how they relate to the overall research process remains a mystery. The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It established the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. An understanding of the philosophical assumptions behind qualitative research begins with assessing where it fits within the overall process of research, noting its importance as an element of research, and considering how to actively write it into a study. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types were elaborated below. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being the researchers he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an insider, thus the researcher assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Moreover, conducting a qualitative study means that researchers try to get as close as possible to the participants being studied, and this basically revolves around the epistemological assumption. Therefore, subjective evidence was assembled based on individual views. Hence, conducting studies in the place where the participants live and work was very important for understanding what the participants were saying. The longer researchers stay in the place or get to know the participants, the more they know what they know from firsthand information. In short, the researcher tries to minimize the distance between himself or herself and those being researched. Thus, Epistemological assumption was known to be how researchers know what they know as they try to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. Subjective evidence was assembled based on individual views from research conducted in the field. Ontology, also called the nature of reality, is primarily related to the nature of reality and its characteristics. Researchers embrace the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities by exploring multiple forms of evidence from different individuals' perspectives and experiences. Thus, this part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), the reality is subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. When studying individuals, qualitative researchers conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. For example, when writers compile a phenomenology, they report how individuals participating in the study view their experiences differently (Moustakas, 1994).

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The researcher also made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result, upheld the authenticity of the responses, and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Axiology, on the other hand, refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discussed values that shape the narrative and included their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Researchers make their values known in the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. All researchers bring value to a study, but qualitative researchers make their values known in a study. This is the axiological assumption that characterizes qualitative research. In a qualitative study, the inquirers admit the value-laden nature of the study and actively report their values and biases as well as the value-laden nature of information gathered from the field. The researcher's presence was apparent in the text, and the author admits that the stories voiced represent an interpretation and presentation of the author as much as the subject of the study (Denzin, 1989, as cited by Carnaghan, 2019) The researcher underpinned the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, he or she preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted the answers in light of

the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric means reporting what reality was through the eyes of my research participants. This was important because it meant that the researcher would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The researcher also used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks questions on the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people. The goal of this research study worked well with this definition in trying to understand school heads' experience and others involved in the community collaboration to eliminate them or lessen the misallocation of school support financial needs, particularly in the operating expenses or mandatory expenses, which are more useful and meaningful. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an investigation that has greater depth and breadth than the offered description implied. The author also suggested that information was viewed as only the tip of the iceberg. The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to explore teachers' experiences of integrating technological literacy and 21st-century learning skills inside the classroom and revealed their feelings and ideas about these experiences. Burns and Grove (2003) stated that phenomenology was a philosophy, an approach, or perspective to living, learning, and doing research. The phenomenological research's goal was to capture the lived experiences, to find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced it, and to describe the phenomenon through the composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality was the reality participants involved in the research situations constructed. Carnaghan (2019) finally highlighted that it was a very vital factor to the philosophical assumptions that underlie

qualitative research and to be able to articulate them in a research study. It was helpful in articulating the importance of philosophy in research because it shapes how we formulate our problem and research questions to study and how we seek information to answer the questions. Next, the assumptions are deeply rooted in our training and reinforced by the scholarly community in which we work. This raises the question as to whether key assumptions can change and whether multiple philosophical assumptions can

be used in a given study. Whether multiple assumptions can be taken in a given study, it may be related to the research experiences of the investigator, his or her openness to exploring using differing assumptions, and the acceptability of ideas taken in the larger scientific community of which he or she was a part. On the reverse side, understanding the differences used by a reviewer may enable an author-researcher to resolve points of difference before they become a focal point for critique.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—A qualitative research method was utilized in this study in employing a phenomenological qualitative design. Phenomenological research deals with the study of experiences from the standpoint of different individual as well as considering those taken-for-granted viewpoints and their usual ways of perceiving. It was based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasizes how vital are the personal perspective. Thus, for understanding subjective experiences and gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, this kind of research design is a powerful method. Qualitative Method of research was also considered to describe life experiences and give them meaning as it was a systematic subjective approach. To gain insight; explore the depth, richness, and complexity inherent in the phenomenon. It is primarily described as a soft science, focuses on complex and broad perspectives, holistic, subjective, dialectic, and inductive reasoning, the basis of knowing is primarily on meaning and discovery, develops theory, shared interpretation, communication, and observation, and the basic element of analysis is on words. To describe experiences as they were lived, qualitative research examines the uniqueness of an individual's lived situations since each person has their own reality; reality is subjective while according to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design

is a qualitative type of research for which interviews are provided in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and helped grasp the subjects' perspective. Agreeing with Creswell (2013), as cited by Chambers (2013), on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group, phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research. To arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon serves as the principal aim of this kind of research approach. Typically, interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data was then read, reread, and culled for phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning. Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. The qualitative research explored and described the experiences of teachers and others involved in the community. The research technique used was a modified van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to capture the teachers' experience. Qualitative research design was a research method used extensively by scientists and researchers

studying human behavior, opinions, themes and motivations. It was said to be the oldest of all techniques, where the ancient Greek philosophers qualitatively observing the world around them and trying to understand and explain what they saw. While qualitative methods are sometimes assumed to be easier than other methods of research, however, information on the conduct of qualitative research provides a depth of understanding about phenomena that cannot be achieved in other ways. Added to this, Shuttleworth, and Wilson, (2008) stated that probably the most flexible type of research design was qualitative research, among the various experimental techniques, encompassing a variety of accepted methods and structures considering its usefulness when a pain hypothesis was utilized in a more complex and broad subject and at the same time yields data that was richer and more insightful into underlying reasons and patterns within phenomena. Phenomenological research on the other hand, seeks to tend to such matters of existence as this in order to reunite the critical illness survivor to their original world. It tends to unhide things of existence, such as facets of awareness like intuition and feeling, which could often be overlooked. These things could only be realized through phenomenological awareness. Phenomenology unveils original experience and its meaning. In so doing, phenomenology offers a deeper understanding that could bring about an individual's perception of a certain topic. Phenomenology foregrounds human experience and brings a holistic approach to human treatment. This kind of research inquiry seeks to understand the human experience from an individual's perspective in contrary to the objectifying and reductionist nature of empiricist research methods (Tembo, 2016). Moreover, Qutoshi (2018), phenomenology as a philosophy and a method of inquiry was not limited to an approach to knowing; it

was rather an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning-making that was used to understand the lived world of human beings on a conscious level. Historically, it was a science of understanding human beings at a deeper level by gazing at the phenomenon. Using this approach, a researcher used bracketing as a taken-for-granted assumption in describing the natural way of the appearance of phenomena to gain insights into lived experiences and interpret them for meaning-making. Phenomenology's advantages include a better understanding of people's meanings and its contribution to the development of new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly, Schutz (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach was to illuminate the specific to identify phenomena through how they are perceived by the actors in a situation. In the human sphere, this translates typically into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing it from the perspective of the research participant. Phenomenology was concerned with the study of experience from the perspective of the individual, 'bracketing' taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant in understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom.

2.4. *Research Participants—*

This study focused on the analysis of the experiences of the teachers on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom. The researcher collected data from ten (10) public elementary teachers assigned at the five (5) respective schools located in Bunawan District, Division of Davao City. Furthermore, the researcher chose two (2) informants from the said schools who are said to be beginning teachers with at least three to five years of teaching service and have experiences of being observed in the classroom. The researcher desired an extensive gathering of ideas from the key informants. This research also chose purposive sampling to certify that the informants are reliable and knowledgeable and possess a lot of experience on the research topic. Further, the purposive sampling also guaranteed the quality of data that was collected and adequate infor-

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were vital to the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations were specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher needed to promote the aims of the research, impart factual knowledge and truth, and prevent error. Social Value. Research is essential to society. In this study, the social value focused on the experienced of teachers in handling fast learners as this study was conducted explicitly among the elementary. Thus, the social problem that pushed the interest of the researcher was the challenges faced by the teachers towards the teachers' experience and others involved in the community collaboration to eliminate them or lessen the problem of dropping out of the schools, whether their strategies or program were good enough. This study could serve as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions

mation; thus, the said purposive sampling was used in this study. To protect against bias and provide a permanent record of what was being said and not said, all interviews were taped, recorded, and transcribed verbatim afterward. To help in the process of data analysis, thoughts, and ideas about the interview also helped make field notes during and immediately after each interview about observation. A good quality multi-directional external microphone was used for the recording of focus groups; as internal microphones are useful to cope with the variation in volume of different speakers. If observers were present, they were introduced to the participants as someone who was just there to observe and often also took notes. Videotaping requires more than one camera to capture the whole group, as well as additional operational personnel in the room (Chadwick, et. al., 2008).

where classroom teachers benefit. Informed Consent. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness-to-participate-in-the-study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants are expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Informed consent and voluntary participation. The process of obtaining consent consisted of the following: consent should be

given voluntarily, subjects should understand the questions that were provided to them, and the persons that were involved must be competent to consent. Thus, to participate in a research study, participants need to be adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information, and have the power of freedom of choice to allow them to decide whether to participate or decline, and all participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached one by one and were given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were given an appropriate time to ask questions and address any concerns. It was explained that as their participation was voluntary, refusing to participate in the study while it was in progress would not affect their care. A participant's information sheet was provided to further explain the study. The potential participants were given appropriate time (in this case: 24 hours up to one week to read the information sheet and to decide whether or not they wanted to be involved in this study. They were required to sign the informed consent form before the interview to indicate their permission to be part of the study, and this signature was confirmed prior to the interview session. Arifin (2018) also added. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate was ensured that participation in the research is entirely voluntary in nature, and based on an understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection are being lodged in the appendices of this study. The vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were deemed capable of answering the research instrument because they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that the researcher could be easily reached through contact number and address in case there were any clarifications or questions

about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents is free of coercion, undue influence or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the possible questions of the respondents. Furthermore, if respondents experienced possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher also ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherited from this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed outputs that were carried out from this study were kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there was no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, must be avoided. Anonymity and Confidentiality. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis, and reporting of the study findings. Privacy and confidentiality of the interview environment were managed care-

fully during telephone communication, interview sessions, data analysis, and dissemination of the findings. Justice. The respondents were informed of my role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to be fully honest in answering the survey questions and that any type of communication about the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The results of the study could be accessed by the respondents, and heads of the participating schools because the information is available, and was placed on CD or other storage devices which can be requested from the researcher to provide. Also, by learning about the results of the study, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher also had the required qualifications to conduct the study. He or she had completed the academic requirements, passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain his or her master's de-

gree, and proved to have the quality to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that my study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. As the researcher, he or she strived that the study was completed successfully in the specified time and that it was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would be of help in the enhancement of the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher has ensured that there were enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed in the target time. Community Involvement. As the researcher, he or she showed respect to the local tradition, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher deemed that it was necessary to express my great pleasure for their whole-hearted participation in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher, I would respect other works by adequately citing the author and rewrite what someone else has said in my way. Understand the context of the study and avoid copy-paste the text verbatim from the reference paper. Always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, I would assure them that honesty in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation in the study and making up of data and/or results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—To establish the credibility, transferability, and dependability of the study, the researcher applied qualitative analysis. The experiences of the participants

were collected and investigated by means of one-on-one non-structured interviews, audio tapes, field notes, and peer debriefing. The said audio tape one-on-one, structured interview, peer de-

briefing, and field notes were performed within 4 days by participants, with each session lasting between 1 hour and 15 minutes. Interview Guide. To gather additional information and supporting answers in order to validate the findings of the study, the researcher prepared 3 open-ended questions in the unstructured type of interview. The interview questions were inclined to the components contained in the questionnaire. Unstructured interviews did not reflect any pre-conceived theories or ideas and were performed with little or no organization. Their usage was generally only with significant depth, or virtually nothing was known about the subject area, or a different perspective of a known subject area was required. The purpose of the research interview is to explore the views, experiences, beliefs, and or motivations of individuals on specific matters. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, are believed to provide a deeper un-

derstanding of social phenomena than would be obtained from purely quantitative methods, such as questionnaires (Stewart et. al., 2008) A questionnaire was a set of carefully designed, written down, and tested questions that were asked of individual respondents to gather information in research (Enon, 2008). The questionnaires were also an appropriate way to collect large amounts of data within a short time. The open-ended questions gave the respondents the opportunity to provide further opinions by qualifying or substantiating their answers. They were intended to tap as much information as possible from the different categories of respondents. O’Leary (2014) also added that questionnaires most notably discover what the masses are thinking. These include market research, political polling, customer service feedback, evaluations, opinion polls, and social science research.

2.7. *Data Collection*—In gathering information, the researcher personally conducted the in-depth interview of participants and saturated the information through one-on-one interviews. Interviewing refers to structured or unstructured verbal communication between the researcher and the participants. The conduct of the interview was done in a conducive, quiet environment, meaning it was free from disturbance, and the participants felt safe in the environment. The interview was initiated individually for about 30 to 40 minutes. In light of the principles of decorum and standards, the researcher adheres to the following steps in the conduct of the interview and focus group discussion first make an appointment with the participants, second prepare a quiet room conducive to conversation, third was to arrange chairs to enhance a face-to-face interviewing, next was to prepare a voice recorder, and lastly, to provide a jar of water. Before conducting the interview, the researcher thanked the participants for their time

and willingness to take part in the study. The researcher informed the participants of the agreement and explained that the interview was unstructured and that probing questions were determined by the information given by the participants. The researcher secured the permission of the participants to record the interview (Talbot, 2005). Other than that, the researcher also stimulated conversations and reactions through the focus group discussion since focus groups may share many common features with less structured interviews. However, there is more to them than merely collecting similar data from many participants at once. A focus group was a group discussion on a particular topic organized for research purposes (Chadwick et al., 2008). Thematic Content Analysis. Anderson (1998) defines thematic content analysis (TCA) as a descriptive presentation of qualitative data. Interview transcripts from research participants or other identifiable writings that reflect experientially on the topic of investigation are exam-

ples of qualitative data. Textural data may be accompanied by video, image, or other types of data. However, this explanation of Thematic Content Analysis was limited to textual data. By detecting similar themes in the texts presented for analysis, thematic content analysis depicts the thematic content of interview transcripts. It was the most fundamental of qualitative analytic processes, and it informs all qualitative analytic procedures and, in some way, informs all qualitative methods. The researcher's epistemological perspective is objective or objectivistic when conducting a Thematic Content Analysis. To express the commonality of voices across

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In analyzing the data, the researcher adopted the steps utilized by Anderson (1998). Before beginning a Thematic Content Analysis, the researcher made multiple copies of the interview transcript or other extant text, including post-interview notes as relevant and stipulated in the Methodology. Next, the researcher marked all descriptions that were relevant to the topic of inquiry with a highlighter. From the highlighted areas, mark each distinct unit of meaning. Meaning units are separated by a break or change in meaning. However, the researcher made sure to retain all information relevant to understanding a meaning unit within the meaning unit. Units may vary in text length. Label each pile as initial categories or themes using keywords or phrases copied from highlighted texts. Revise categories as you continue to code data. Then, if obvious information is missing from the text, the researcher identifies categories that are missing and goes through the entire interview transcript, identifying distinct units, grouping and regrouping similar and dissimilar units, and re-labeling categories for each additional interview transcript, using the Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) as indicated on the steps highlighted above. Afterwards, when all Thematic Content Analysis were complete,

participants, the researcher groups and distills a list of similar themes from the texts. Every reasonable effort is made to use labels for topics derived from participants' actual words and to group themes in a way that directly reflects the texts as a whole. While selecting and identifying themes does necessitate some interpretation, it is kept to a bare minimum. The researcher's personal views and thoughts about the themes, or what the Thematic Content Analysis themes might mean, are essentially irrelevant to the Thematic Content Analysis (Anderson, 1998) also affirmed.

the researcher read each Thematic Content Analysis separately. While retaining meaning units, combine categories or themes for all interview transcripts and notes. Collapse or subdivide categories as appropriate. Re-label categories as appropriate. After a few days, the researcher reread the total categories as a whole. Consider whether too many or too few categories made overall sense of the interview transcripts given on the topic. Redo all the instructions above until the researcher is satisfied that the categories reflect the interview transcripts as a whole. Environmental Triangulation. A significant humanistic, interactional, and empathic aspect characterizes qualitative research. This type of study focuses on a set of meanings, values, beliefs, and social behaviors that aren't easily quantified. Qualitative studies in the health field allow researchers to understand the perspectives of users, professionals, and managers on a variety of issues impacting the services and treatment provided to experience health, illness, and death, among other situations (Minayo and Guerriero, 2012). Ullrich et al. (2012) also added that due to the characteristics that underlie qualitative research, it was constantly questioned regarding its scientific rigor, which was linked to the criteria of reliability, validity,

and generality used in its development. These objections, on the other hand, are based on quantitative assumptions that do not correspond to the goals of qualitative research, which are to understand, analyze, and describe a specific occurrence rather than to measure or quantify it. Moreover, Heale, and Noble (2019) mentioned that in a research study, triangulation was a technique for enhancing the credibility and validity of research findings. Validity is concerned with the extent to which a study accurately reflects or evaluates the notion or concepts being explored; credibility relates to trustworthiness and how convincing a study was. In a research project, triangulation can help ensure that basic biases stemming from the use of a single method or observer were overcome by mixing theories, methods, or observers. Environmental triangulation entails the utilization of multiple locations, settings, and other essential aspects connected to the study's environment, such as time, day, and season. The objective was to

figure out whether environmental elements, if any, might have an impact on the data collected throughout the study. If the results are consistent under different environmental situations, then validity has been established. It was only used when it was likely that the findings may be influenced by environmental factors. Thus, the research is conducted at Bunawan District, Division of Davao City. The environment provided by the researcher to the participants facilitated a more significant space, while the more restricted environment provided for thematic oral history provided a more qualified and receptive listening space, stimulating the in-depth analysis of more intimate issues. Added to, it was observed that, even in the face of environmental changes (time, day, place), the key information for the participants' experiences remained the same, and the only aspect that changed was the level of information, which, in turn, were evident with a greater or lesser extent under certain circumstances.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—It was shown in the analytical framework the experiences of teachers in their apprehensions on the classroom observation tool as this helped them improve the teaching pedagogy and bring a new perspective on how to cope with the challenges that the teachers face during the classroom observations. The experiences were analyzed to bring out their perceptions and feelings to make a difference in the educational system. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Figure 2 shows procedures undertaken to analyze the textual data. Collected transcripts were listened to and transcribed with a list of significant statements that would be developed from them and grouped into larger units of information called "meaning tunings"

or themes (Creswell, 2007). With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions to remain faithful to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes were typically formed by grouping units of meaning (Creswell, 1998). Moustakas (1984) described writing a description. Next, a structural description was written about the experience, reflecting on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced (Creswell, 2007). Finally, a composite description of the phenomenon was written; this is the essence of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of the phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007). The researcher then collected data from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via

lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization that extracted significant statements from transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his/her meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. The study's conceptual framework showed that teachers' experiences regarding understanding their mental well-being in a workplace through a support system are taken into account, unveiling and bringing another hope and viewpoint to a similar situation or case. The teachers' experiences were analyzed to reveal their insights and feelings and make a difference in the educational system. This aims to provide information and ideas on how the development of a collaborative support system for teachers affects their professional development and the higher context. The data collected during interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed to search for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. Using semi-structured in-depth interviews, the experiences of the teachers were investigated after the signing of consent forms. Figure 2 shows procedures undertaken to

analyze the organized textual data. With list of significant statements that was developed from the transcripts and is then grouped into larger units of information called meaning tunings or themes. The organized data were collected, listened to, and recorded (Creswell, 2007). The researcher was in need to continue to bracket any assumptions to remain true to the phenomenon with the list of non-redundant units of meaning. The researcher will also rigorously examine these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context (Groenewald, 2004). To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (cited in (Sanders, 2003; Speziale Carpenter, 2007); Each transcript should be read and re-read to obtain a general sense of the whole content; significant statements about the phenomenon under study should be extracted from each transcript. These statements must be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their page and line numbers; meanings should be formulated from these significant statements, and the formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes; the findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study; the fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described. Finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher's descriptive results with their experiences.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Qualitative content analysis was commonly used to analyze qualitative data. However, few articles have examined the trustworthiness of its use in nursing science studies. Qualitative content analysis's trustworthiness is often presented

using terms such as credibility, dependability, conformability, transferability, and authenticity. This article focuses on trustworthiness based on a review of previous studies, our own experiences, and methodological textbooks. Trustworthiness was described for the main qualita-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

tive content analysis phases, from data collection to reporting of the results. The researcher concluded that it is important to scrutinize the trustworthiness of every phase of the analysis process, including the preparation, organization, and reporting of results. Together, these phases should give a reader a clear indication of the overall trustworthiness of the study. The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Moreover, in qualitative studies, it was pertinent to address how qualitative researchers establish that the research study's findings are credible, transferable, confirmable, and dependable. Trustworthiness was all about establishing these four things, which were described in more detail below. Transferability was how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study's findings were applicable to other contexts. In this case, other contexts can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. Qualitative researchers can use thick descriptions to show that the research study's findings can apply to other contexts, circumstances, and situations. Dependability was the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. This boils down to how the findings are true and accurate. Qualitative researchers can use triangulation to show that the research study's findings are credible. Finally, Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings were based on participants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a particular narrative. To establish confirmability, qualitative researchers could provide an audit trail, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the thematic analysis of the interview data. It presents themes that emerge from the analysis. Along with the themes are figures and comprehensive discussions that answer the objectives of the study. This chapter discusses the themes that emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presented the description and background of the participants who assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. The live experiences of teachers on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom—

Based on the data gathered during the interview, the participants' experiences of teachers on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom were coded, and the following themes. A strong relationship exists between fostering active learning and technology literacy in the classroom. Learners who use technology to learn exhibit higher levels of interest in their learning as well as increased participation. Teachers can design engaging

and interactive classes that empower students to take charge of their education by incorporating technology resources. Technology literacy and active learning work together to develop the critical thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving abilities necessary for success in the modern world. Using technology in the classroom helps students become lifelong learners in a society that is becoming increasingly digitally dependent. It goes beyond simply staying current.

3.1.1. Active Learning Process—This aligns with the study Macho (2005) demonstrated how integrating technology into the classroom improves student learning. Most educators in this research concur that technology literacy enhances classroom management because learners are more disciplined and attentive. Additionally, this study demonstrated that pupils learn better when they use technology, and lessons built with technology are more interesting and engaging. Consequently, the attendees decided that incorporating ICT can support students' education. Added to this aligns with the research findings of Zhang (2013), in which the majority of educators believe it is helpful to include technological literacy into the classroom for learners. Technology literacy helps students become more creative and imaginative as their knowledge paradigm expands; technology literacy helps students possess all four skills in learning when they are able to acquire necessary information and knowledge; and finally, this helps students develop the confidence to have better communication and be able to ex-

press their thoughts and ideas. In other words, one of teachers' experiences in the teaching and learning process is that they produce and exemplify ultimate teaching competence and skills when teachers are equipped with technology literacy. These justify the congruence of teaching competence to active participation in the class. It is accentuated that as teachers excel in the use of interactive media inside the class, students tend to engage more and perform well inside the class since they are inclined in the field of different interactive media instruction. As the researchers, one of the teachers' experiences highlighted in the interview is improved teaching performance. Teachers are indeed suppressed by the dilemma of the decline of teaching performance, which leads to the poor performance of the students and the weak institutional organization. Thus, it is indeed a factor that the teachers should brainstorm innovative ways to diminish that said problem and the thing being stressed during the interview is the use of technology literacy as a bridge to connect the teaching performance as well the teaching process to provide meaningful learning to the students.

3.1.2. Improved Instructional Process of Teachers—According to Tazci (2011), the majority of teachers think that integration is effective, but the technology tools available in schools are neither sufficient nor in good condition; teachers do not receive enough profes-

sional development training; technical support is provided, but it could be improved occasionally; and the school's computer lab is not in very good condition with well-functioning tools and facilities. Moreover, to effectively plan for the integration of computers and information

Fig. 3. The live experiences of teachers on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom

technology into the teaching and learning process, teachers should collaborate both within and across disciplines. Teachers should integrate technology that can improve student learning into their lesson plans and learning activities both within and across disciplines as soon as they become available. In order to complement their acquisition of knowledge and other abilities, they will also build information technology skills through an activity-based, project-driven learning methodology. (Ministry of Education in Ontario, 2000) This study shows a strong correlation between improved teaching performance among educators and technology literacy. Teachers with strong technological skills prepare lessons more efficiently and use resources and classroom management techniques more effectively. By incorporating technology into the

classroom, educators may create more dynamic, engaging classes that cater to a range of learning preferences and create an inclusive learning environment. Technology also makes real-time feedback and evaluation processes possible, which helps teachers better monitor students' progress and adjust their lessons. In the end, adopting technology into the classroom helps educators adjust to the changing nature of education and makes them more successful in fostering student learning outcomes. Figure 3 shows the live experiences of teachers on technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom and the emergence of the two themes: efficiency of the instructional process, active learning process, and improved instructional process of teachers.

3.2. *Teachers cope with challenges in technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom —*

In this research question, the teachers accentuated as they cope with the challenges of technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom. To summarize, based on the information given by the informants, it is very clear that teachers work hard to provide

3.2.1. Effective Teaching Skills—This is parallel to the statement of Niess (2005), as cited by Kouser, Shazia Majid, and Ishfaq (2021), that while using technology in the classroom makes learning enjoyable and engaging for the students, it also allows them to learn at their own pace, anywhere, at any time. With the aid of technology, they can readily access the knowledge they want to learn. It's not always the case that teachers should teach their students in the twenty-first century in the same method that they learnt the material. Also, the majority of teachers concurred that using technology will undoubtedly present many opportunities for successful teaching, and technology literacy-supported instruction makes learning more effective. This scenario demonstrates how educators see the good aspects of using technology in the teaching and learning process, wherein teachers use it as a tool to ensure

3.2.2. Provides Differentiated Instruction—This context matches the idea of Tomlinson (2001) that when teachers intentionally incorporate technology into their lessons, they frequently do so to diversify instruction by employing particular techniques that support students in becoming lifelong learners. The practice of using a range of teaching techniques to address the needs of a varied population of pupils is known as differentiated instruction. To enable each student to learn efficiently, many channels for content acquisition, idea processing and development, and product development are thus offered to them. Through my research,

the students with adequate firsthand experience to satiate their yearning for eye-opening and interest-building activities, and this could be achieved by incorporating the instructional process with interactive media.

that the process is both successful and efficient. Subsequently, based on the collected data, it is also evident that the use of ICT in the classroom encourages students to participate more actively in the teacher's lesson plans. This is a result of the student's familiarity with technology literacy, which makes learning easier for them and enables them to be engaged more in the lesson (Ghavifekr and Rosdy, 2015). It is indeed a reality that teachers nowadays do not settle for dull performances inside the classroom. Instead, they are armed with sufficiency by equating their performances with meaningful activities, and that sufficiency is procured only with the use of interactive media in the classes. Lessons joined with different technological advancements and intricate materials, awaken their inner curiosities to learn, as this is influenced by the advancements of the technology being used.

I've discovered that the use of differentiated instruction in the classroom is significantly impacted by technology literacy. Teachers with digital skills can tailor lessons to each student in the classroom, considering their varied requirements and ability levels. Teachers can provide students with a variety of activities, assessments, and information that are suited to their unique learning preferences and styles by using digital platforms and tools. With the use of technology, teachers can easily modify their lesson plans and give pupils individualized attention and enrichment activities at their own speed. Ultimately, digital literacy gives teachers

the tools they need to establish a welcoming classroom where all students may succeed and realize their potential. Based on the statement provided by the respondents, it is clear that poor internet access is a major barrier to good instruction. Instructors need to adjust by using other teaching strategies that don't mainly rely on resources found online. This can entail making use of offline resources, including locally stored instructional videos, printed worksheets, and textbooks. Instructors frequently preload inter-

net content during off-peak hours to guarantee availability during class time. Addressing this issue also requires working with local government and school authorities to promote better internet infrastructure. Notwithstanding the difficulties, Filipino educators show fortitude and resourcefulness in overcoming the constraints placed on them by sluggish internet connections in order to carry on offering high-quality instruction.

3.2.3. Slow Internet Connection—According to Hossain and Rahman (2017), students should make better use of the Internet as part of their coursework, and the institution should offer a conducive environment and Internet access since 82 of the students in their study utilize the Internet for academic purposes. However, Serhan (2020) revealed unfavorable findings about attitudes toward using online learning management systems. With these concepts and details, internet access becomes a problem and a task for professors, the institution, and students alike. This has been a predicament for the teachers, particularly in technology literacy since we do not have a stable internet connection. Slow internet connections pose serious problems for Filipino teachers, methods. To lessen the dependency on internet access,

they first make use of offline resources including downloaded instructional videos, interactive multimedia presentations, and offline learning apps. Second, educators use a blended learning strategy that combines technology-mediated training with conventional teaching techniques to give students freedom in getting their lessons, even when they are not online. Finally, they prioritize professional growth in digital skills, arming themselves with various tools and techniques to adjust to fluctuating internet connections without compromising the caliber of instruction. Figure 4 shows the teacher's coping with challenges in technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom and the emergence of the three themes: efficiency of the instructional process, slow internet connection, and differentiated instruction for the students.

3.3. Educational Insights generated from technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom—During the in-depth interview, many themes and realizations emerged that were underpinned and unlocked. One realization was that there were insights that could be generated regarding technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom. Based on the notions of the teachers mentioned above, it is indeed highlighted

that teachers, in order to effectively engage students and improve their teaching methods, must have access to technological resources in the classroom. With the help of these resources, teachers may design dynamic lesson plans that accommodate a range of learning preferences and interactive learning experiences. Through the integration of technology, educators may leverage an abundance of tools, including virtual simulations, multimedia presentations, and

Fig. 4. Teachers cope with challenges in the technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom

educational apps, to enhance the immersive and effective nature of their lessons. Technology also gives teachers the ability to monitor student progress, tailor their lessons, and give timely feedback—all of which help to create a positive learning environment. In the end, providing teachers with technology tools helps them better prepare their pupils for the demands of the digital age and navigate the changing educational landscape. In other words, interactive media is indeed a trend in the educational sys-

tem nowadays as it is integrated into the 21st-century teaching and learning process. However, the problem exists because of the insufficiency of the learning materials given to the teachers. Thus, the said trend is being declined by the students as well as the teaching competence of the teachers since the materials are lacking. It is a trending issue in the field of education, the scarcity of materials. This is a trending topic that the higher sector must look into.

3.3.1. Enough Technological Tools—Teachers use Interactive media applications to make presentations on a particular subject. This helps to encourage students to learn particular subjects effectively. These presentations combine several different media elements. Interactive media applications with learning platforms are programmed to simulate different situations and help students to understand difficult subjects easily. They help students to understand the most relevant parts of that

subject. Interactive media applications also help teachers to prepare teaching materials in less time than it would take without the use of such applications. This also corresponds to the idea that the application of technology in the educational sector has been used to improve and make the teaching-learning process more appropriate, effective, and efficient for both teachers and students in order to successfully complete a variety of activities and tasks in various sectors, such as the educational sector.

Today's students are fortunate to have access to a wide range of technological tools and Internet resources (Baytak et al., 2011). Added to, while using technology in the classroom makes learning enjoyable and engaging for the students, it also allows them to learn at their own pace, anywhere, at any time. With the aid of technology, they can readily access the knowledge they want to learn. According to Niess (2005). How teachers learn subject matter is not necessarily the way their students will need to be taught in the 21st century. The integration of technology in education has the potential to enhance student performance and yield favorable learning results. As the respondents stated, teachers who attend training and seminars will be better equipped to integrate technology into their

3.3.2. Join Training and Seminars—The relevant study by Ertmer and Ottenbreit-Leftwich (2013) emphasizes the significance of offering instructors computer literacy training and seminars. This study highlights that although having access to technology is crucial, teachers also require sufficient guidance and assistance in order to successfully incorporate technology into their lesson plans. It makes the case that workshops and seminars, as well as other professional development programs, are crucial in assisting educators in gaining the know-how and abilities required for successful technology integration. The study emphasizes how crucial it is to provide instructors with continual assistance and reflection opportuni-

3.3.3. Enhanced Teaching Competence—The rate at which technology is developing in society and schools has been exponential and will remain so. Teachers use technology to help them provide structure and guidance to their pupils, monitor their development, and assess their work. Students are using technology for

lessons and will have a greater understanding of technology. These workshops give teachers practical information and hands-on practice using digital tools for teaching. Teachers stay abreast of the most recent developments in educational technology through chances for continuous learning, which guarantees their continued proficiency in its usage. Furthermore, trainings encourage networking and cooperation among teachers, giving them the chance to exchange creative ideas and best practices for incorporating technology into the classroom. In the end, funding workshops and training to increase teachers' technical literacy improves instruction and gets pupils ready for success in a world that is becoming more and more digital.

ties so they may effectively and confidently use technology to improve student learning (Ertmer Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2013). To summarize, engaging in further training, seminars, and workshops has been the predominant factor in the success of the teaching process. Indeed, the researcher observed that teachers, as they indulge in the field of teaching, do not acquire ultimate skills immediately. However, they are required to associate with various trainings. They require a lot of teaching experience to develop teaching skills and practice. Teachers are obliged to deliver instruction that respects the students' multiple intelligences and varied learning styles. This is a win-win situation for both teachers and students.

research projects, data analysis, issue solving, product design, and work evaluation. Students can collaborate with one another to generate and share new insights and knowledge. The learning strategies are grounded in theories of learning that enable educators to offer their pupils a variety of learning opportunities. As time passes,

Fig. 5. Educational Insights generated from technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom

technology and our understanding of how to use it efficiently change constantly. To support students' learning, teachers need to gain experience and knowledge in using technology (Kouser Majid, 2021). Most people believe that technological applications can wipe out humans from current traditional in-class teaching activities. However, this is not true. In reality, a more stable environment is achieved with the use of interactive media applications. Negative influences, which affect teachers' psychology, decrease, and teaching quality is enhanced with the help of these interactive media applications. Additionally, users earn at any convenient time

and under any circumstances using this application. Technology literacy, like all other teaching techniques, should be used judiciously in the learning process. Media can be used to motivate discussions or lock in concepts. However, there are a number of important considerations for faculty before they integrate media or ask their students to use or develop media in their courses. Figure 5 shows the educational insights generated from technology literacy as 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom and the emergence of the three themes: enough technological tools, joining trainings and seminars, and enhanced teaching performance.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the field of teacher experiences that have reinvented the classroom setting were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—

The main objective of this study was to analyze how teachers cope with the challenges of accentuating 21st-century teaching skills inside the classroom, particularly technological literacy, through their experiences. There were two themes for Figure Three, which were described as the live experiences of the teachers. Teachers mentioned and revealed during the interview, namely, improved instructional and active learning processes. The live experiences of the teachers were highlighted using the effective teaching strategies of the teachers in delivering the different instruction to the students. In return, the students also perform well in their classes. This was an overall mirror of the educational system's success as embodied by active learners and enriched teaching competencies. Meanwhile, the teachers grasped the fourth figure with two themes as they described how they showcased their teaching competence regarding interactive media instruction, which ameliorates their teaching competence. First was the teaching process's efficiency, the students' differentiated instruction, and the slow internet connection. This was indeed a good combination for the educational system to im-

prove its delivery of instructional processes to its clientele, the students. Lastly, figure five, in the educational insight of the teachers, exemplifies three themes drawn and observed during the interview. These were enough technological tools, enhanced teaching performance, and joining training and seminars. From the teachers' perspectives, it was clearly shown that interactive media instruction has various qualities that affect the teachers by providing them the backbone to be effective in their chosen field. Moreover, not only do teachers benefit from interactive media instruction, but also the students experience active participation during discussions and activities. Thus, the Department of Education should consider these matters and listen to the voices of the teachers because teachers are at the forefront of the services and work of all programs offered by the department. They were the implementers who experienced a lot of positive and negative feedback from the parents and stakeholders. Sometimes, teachers were shocked absorbers, so let us understand that teachers made them happy and at ease by unloading them with loads of work.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The Department of Education has imparted different programs to help learners access data information. Then, the teacher was the implementer with overworking hours at school due to the volume of DepEd policies, and orders with some policies were redundant. This problem has been around for a long time. With the result of this interview, there were live teachers' experiences and insights. However, life was full of surprises, so things sometimes were good for the teachers as their responses showed innovations in work. Technology literacy has been a trend in the educational field for a long time. It has been a trademark of many teachers

in upgrading the systematized instruction process. Additionally, it takes many forms, making it very adaptable and flexible. Technology literacy instruction could become a book, a CD tape, video clips, magazine, laptops, a projector, and many more that could eventually help upgrade the instructional process and develop skills, particularly skills such as digital citizenship, critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision making; creativity and innovation; communication and collaboration; research and information fluency; and technology operations and concepts. On the other hand, teacher competence is also a crucial topic in education. Sometimes, teachers suffer from depression due to poor competence, especially when delivering

instruction. The fourth figure, with themes of efficiency of the teaching process and, finally, the differentiated instruction for the students, was grasped from the teachers describing teachers showcasing their teaching competence through technology literacy inside the classroom. The efficiency of the teaching process can be called successful when it delivers the instruction and discussion to the students effectively by providing them with meaningful learning experiences that would cater to the student's readiness to face real-life situations. Finally, for the insights given by the teachers concerning technology literacy inside the classroom, they highlighted

4.3. Future Directions—This study was significant to principals. In it, principals could reveal their lived experiences in implementing educational policies in the school, especially in this new standard setting. They could also adopt the teachers' coping practices regarding their challenges. Furthermore, it may recommended that divisions and school districts observe these practices so that students and teachers can benefit from them. They should encourage teachers to use different interactive media instruction and materials to provide quality services to learners. School heads and Administrators. The data and information collected in this study would serve as a platform for the school heads and administrators to create dynamic schemes in their supervision of school activities for the betterment of

the stipulation of enough learning materials, enhanced teaching performance, and addressed various learning styles of the students. This theme was an opportunity for teachers not to be burdened with the traditional way of teaching but instead to grow professionally by acclimatizing how students learn. These common themes were observed during the researcher's interview. These were essential themes that everyone must understand to achieve their vision, mission, and goal of delivering quality education to the learners. The school's success must rely on these kinds of essential themes.

the school and of the teachers by helping them grow. Particularly, the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influences the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency of the teachers. They can also motivate the teachers to keep their burning passion for serving this generation's young minds. Teachers. This study would also be significant because the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influences the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency of teachers. It also improves their teaching competencies and helps them proceed with the teaching and learning process effectively as they serve as the wheel of education and the facilitator of learning. Lastly, this study would serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

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